

THE ROLE OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGY IN SHAPING NATIONAL IDENTITY THROUGH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role of linguoculturology in shaping national identity through language. The study of this problem helps to identify the features of the crisis of modern society, which influences the formation and change of national identity. The features of cultural and cognitive dominants of the subculture of areas that influence the formation of national sovereignty are studied.

Language and culture are closely related, because language not only reflects the cultural characteristics of a people, its history and worldview, but also actively participates in the creation of a cultural fund through fiction and scientific works. As many scientists have argued, language is not only a product of culture, but also its important component, as well as a necessary condition for its existence. Language acts as a mechanism that forms cultural codes and contributes to the dynamics of cultural development. One of the most pressing issues in modern linguistic research is the problem of national identity. Language, being not only a means of reflecting identity but also of creating it, forms the most important function of language. National identity is a sense of "a nation as a coherent whole, represented by unique traditions, culture and language" [1]. National identity can be attributed to a person's subjective feeling, which he shares with a group of people about a nation, regardless of his legal status of citizenship. National identity can be considered from the point of view of psychology as "awareness of difference", "a feeling and awareness of "we" and "they" [3]. Scientists who are particularly interested in the problem of national identity explain this by several circumstances. In the context of globalization, the way of interpreting the concept of "identity" has changed. An in-depth study of this problem helps to identify the features of the crisis of modern society, which influences the formation and change of national identity. The reassessment of values, which previously formed the basis of human identification in society, has accelerated the crisis of culture as a whole. Scientific studies of literature reflect many concepts of identity. The term "identity" has been used in the works of Western philosophers, from the ancient Greeks to modern theoretical philosophy. The term "identity" comes from the Latin word *identifico* - "I identify". Sigmund Freud believed that "the process of identification appears to be a mechanism that ensures the formation of personality, and is interpreted as an individual's experience of his or her similarity to another subject or object of reality" [4].

The term "national identity" has become established in the socio-philosophical discourse at the end of the XX century and is considered from the point of view of the approaches of various scientific schools (classical psychoanalysis, German, French). In existing O'zbek and Russian research papers, including dissertations, devoted to this problem, this concept is defined as "a complex, multidimensional and versatile social phenomenon in its essence", "a deeply rooted symbolic space, thanks to the analysis of psychological, cultural, historical, territorial and political dimensions" [1]. "National identity" is a multifaceted concept and consists of a number of important ideological components: "national self-awareness and mentality, national character, historical memory, ethno-national images, national traditions, myths, symbols and behavioral stereotypes" [5]. Significant components of identity are historically formed, relatively formalized and often competing ideas about the country's place in the world, its cultural and civilizational affiliation, and geopolitical priorities.

The problem of national identity is considered in his research works by M. A. Ortikov, a specialist in the problems of identity and culture in international relations, professor, and doctor of sociological sciences. His study "National and Ethnic Identity in the Modern World" is devoted to the concept of national identity from the point of view of various scientific schools. The author also assesses the significance of the analyzed forms of identity in the process of formation and development of modern society. M. A. Ortikov defined national identity as "a cultural norm reflecting the expansive reactions of an individual in relation to his nation and national political system" [4].

Of particular interest is the work of Yu. A. Kozhevnikova "The Crisis of National Identity in a Globalizing World". In it, the author considers national identity from the point of view of a set of various "dimensions" and "attributes". Yu. A. Kozhevnikova defines national identity as a complex, multifaceted and versatile social phenomenon in its essence. National identity is presented as a certain "rooted" symbolic space based on the analysis of psychological, cultural, historical, territorial and political dimensions of national identity. In this space, a community of people turns into a "national community" capable of distinguishing "theirs" from "others". Own culture, a system of moral and social values, cultural norms and ideals are the principles on which identity is built. Yu. A. Kozhevnikova argues that "national identity is a real phenomenon that is subject to various influences, impacts and changes". The author notes that "national identity is a unique unity of its elements, "significant attributes" shared by those who belong to a particular nation" [2].

Consequently, national identity can be "synonymized" with the concepts of "originality", "continuity", "stability", identifying ethnic and national affiliation and characterizing them with qualitative certainty. The "cementing element" of national identity can be considered "regional patriotism", manifested in love for one's region, "identification of the image of the Motherland with the region and the country", in the absence of a desire to change one's place of residence, a feeling of solidarity with fellow countrymen, pride in their achievements, an understanding of responsibility for the development of one's city or village. V. R. Voligin, N. R. Abdullaev distinguish two levels of identity: "the first order - regional, and ... the second order (belonging to a larger community) - all-Russian" [1]. The symbolic connection of the population with space arises as a result of determining the cultural and cognitive dominants of the region's subculture, that is, the key features of various cultural and natural objects of

urban infrastructure, their assessment with "reliance on accepted cultural norms, emotional experience", which presupposes a harmonious combination of "individuality" and "inclusion in society".

In linguacultural studies, there are several approaches to the study of the process of formation of regional identity, explaining the reasons for its consolidation in the consciousness of an individual. The essentialist approach allows us to consider regional identity as a free model of collective self-awareness, which is formed under the influence of extralinguistic factors, primarily territorial, historical, cultural, religious [4]. The constructivist approach emphasizes the purposefulness of modeling, its determinacy by the "cultural policy carried out in the region, the main and dominant actor of which is the regional administration" [5].

In particular, this is associated with the phenomenon of branding the dominants of the region's subculture as significant "territorial assets" that contribute to the popularization of the region, the creation of tourist and economic attractiveness of the city. They traditionally include objects of cultural and historical heritage, natural landscape, and infrastructure elements [3]. Brand symbols are unique units of various semiotic systems, have special semantics and define the "seaborgium of a regional subculture" reflecting the ideas of "the linguacultural community about its own originality, uniqueness in the context of the opposition of one location to another", represented by various sign means. They "form the core of regional identity, since ... they are significant for community members and are interpreted only by them". Regional dominants, reflecting the directions of social development that are important for residents, form the core of national culture, being, among other things, its key signs and symbols. For example, significant dominants:

- for Tashkent: "Tashkent is the heart of Uzbekistan", "Tashkent - the heart of central Asia", "Tashkent is the pearl of the East";
- for Samarkand: "Samarkand is a fairytale city", "Samarkand is an ancient city";
- for Bukhara: "Bukhara is the heart of the desert", "Bukhara is an oriental fairytale";
- for Kharezm: "Kharezm - the Country of a Thousand Fortresses", "Kharezm - an architectural masterpiece of Uzbekistan"; etc.

The presence of a regional idea is a significant cultural resource that influences the dynamics and productivity of the region's development, and is a system-forming factor in the interaction of federal and regional authorities. At the same time, the state of the level balance can serve as an indicator of problems associated with the processes of development of civil society, its self-awareness. Thus, the dominance of regional identity is an indicator of separate sentiments, "the parity of identities can indicate both crisis aspects in the state itself (weak value basis, loss of controllability, etc.), and the inclusion of a special context of consolidation in the region (then the reasons are important) or, conversely, the emergence of sharp polarization in the regional community itself" [4]. Thus, the formation of national identity is a significant process for the existence of the country as a multinational state, a question related to sovereignty. The regional environment creates a basis for possible successful interaction of the existing distinctive subcultures, a mental basis for the acceptance and assimilation of national values, where the connecting links are common historical memory, traditions, and patriotism.

The linguacultural approach to teaching emphasizes that language and culture form a unique space for personal self-expression. The author of the article emphasizes the importance of such teaching, which is aimed at integrating cultural values into students' language training. This allows students not only to master language skills, but also to develop an understanding of cultural symbols, traditions and customs that are an integral part of national identity. Formation of a linguistic personality through cultural aspects of teaching becomes an important element of the educational process. This is especially relevant in teaching a native or foreign language, where language is considered not only as a communication tool, but also as a key to understanding culture, history and mentality. This approach allows us to expand the scope of traditional language education and create deeper and more meaningful connections between students and the language being studied.

Linguacultural analysis shows that language reflects key cultural codes through such elements as mythologemes, symbols and phraseological units, which enhances its role in conveying historical and cultural values. This makes language an important means of preserving and transmitting cultural experience between generations.

In addition, the results of the study emphasize the importance of the cultural aspect in the educational process, especially when teaching a native or foreign language. The linguacultural approach contributes to the formation of a linguistic personality, developing students not only language skills, but also an understanding of the cultural context. This approach allows for a deeper integration of language and culture into the educational program, which in turn enriches the learning process, making it more multifaceted and meaningful for the personal and professional growth of students.

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